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CONTENTS

- **Indian health care delivery system: role of spiritual healing and path of divinity** 192-201
Sushil Kumar Goel
- **Loneliness, social anxiety, social influence and addiction that contributes to online social networking: A study among adolescent in Malaysia** 202-215
Balan Rathakrishnan, Azizi Yahaya, Ismail Maakip, Peter Voo Su Kiong, Soon Singh Bikar Singh, Mohammad Rahim Kamaluddin and Mohammad Amin Wani
- **STEM(ming) of girls' orientation in academia: A Psycho-Social narrative** 216-227
Suruchi Bhatia
- **Development of standardized test on emotional expression based on Bengali population** 228-237
Payel Dey Ghosh, Anwesha Chakrabarti, Kunal Chanda, Soma Mitra and Mallika Banerjee
- **Pubertal timing and externalizing problem behaviors in adolescents: A review of literature** 238-250
Rupan Dhillon and Palak Kanwar
- **Yoga: A complete transformation from burnout towards being healthy** 251-260
Amit Kumar Vishwakarma, Rohit Kumar Maurya and Sandeep Kumar
- **A study of gender differences among invulnerable children** 261-272
Gopal Krishna Nanda and Ashok Kumar Biswal
- **Family-to-work interface and job performance: The moderating influence of conscientiousness** 273-291
Shamini Srivastava
- **Depression and death anxiety among HIV positive persons in relation to self efficacy** 292-303
Lalita, Sandeep Singh and Amit
- **Perceived stress among female adolescents** 304-308
Rasmita Behera
- **Emotion identification, discrimination and expression in encephalitis survivor children** 309-320
Nisha Kumari

STEM(ming) of girls' orientation in academia: A Psycho-Social narrative

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Girls' health, education, empowerment, and their quality of life are some of the important challenges that are relevant in today's world across the nations. Enhancing girls' mental health and their quality of life is one of the challenges for the "World Health Organization", which is influenced in a major way by the kind of education and career they are part of. Girls' education and their entry into workforce have been the central reference point of women empowerment and equality. Though, they are part of the work force in the organized setup since few decades. In the present work we are trying to elucidate the reasons for girls opting for certain courses and hence becoming a part of specific work force. In particular, factors that contribute to these choices and further impact of the choices have been reviewed. Existing research data has been studied to analyse the trends. It is alarming to see the impact of socialization through parents, as well as society at large, on the career choices made by girls. The deliberation highlights the role of collaborative participation of parents and girls, and holistic counselling.

Keywords: Career, education, gender segregation, parenting, self-concept, self-efficacy.

INTRODUCTION

Evolution is not only important to nature but it has also relevance in different aspects of human lives which shapes our understanding of the universe in significant ways. These phenomenon needs to be contextualized in the domain of academics so as changes can be made in cultural and historical interpretations of the concepts of 'equality' and 'equal opportunities'. Equality has emerged as an important concept in 20th century. Earlier, it was regarded as a means of preparing different groups of people for their positions in life (as leaders, bureaucrats, workers and mothers). In the early 19th century, the separation of middle-class family life into masculine and feminine spheres coincided with augmenting division between the sexes in the matter of education. Consequently, males belonging to this socio-economic class left home at an early age for professional training-as suggested by Max Sugar (2104) in his book entitled *Female Adolescent Development*. In fact, Sugar (2014) further quotes the work of Stone (1977) to show that males were stimulated to separate from their mothers, and that this separation constituted the serious task of adult socialization. Thus, given this

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